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Application of Continuing Engineering Education Talent Training Model and Mixed Learning Model Based on the Construction of "Intelligent Chinese Academy of Sciences" in Lifelong Education

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ABSTRACT

The training of talents in continuing engineering education should be closely related to the reality of science and technology development, pay attention to the updating of frontier knowledge, strengthen the cultivation of multi-disciplinary integration and innovation ability, and integrate into project-based teaching, so as to construct a new model of engineering education which aims at practicality and effectiveness. Based on the informatization project of Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS for short), "Intelligent CAS ", we explore a new model of continuing engineering education personnel training with cutting-edge features, and it is guided by the frontier scientific research and technology projects, and supported by the "8+2" fields of the CAS (frontier crossing, advanced materials, energy, life and health, ocean, resources, ecological environment, information, and photovoltaic space, as well as two public support platforms) and based on the multi-terminal lifelong learning environment integrating open education resources. What's more, we study the mixed learning mode which is based on point, line and surface for scientific and technical engineers and integrate online and offline deeply. We design and practice it from teaching objectives, educational models, the three-level knowledge system, and thematic training, so that we can build a long-term, systematic and practical lifelong education mode, which is centered on learners. So far, the CAS has carried out four years of practice to serve nearly 70,000 scientists. The rapid growth of the learning data shows the effective and practical of this model, which conforms to the law of the development of continuing engineering education itself.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of economy and science and technology, the skills required by the labor force in today's world have been constantly redefined. Continuing engineering education urgently needs to deepen the reform of personnel training mode aiming at practicality and effectiveness. Interdisciplinary education is particularly necessary today as future careers are likely to lead graduates from all over the world to work in industries that are currently undefined and undeveloped.

In the field of Higher Engineering Education in the world, the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) of the United States has been acting as the pioneer in the reform. After the new century, it has launched three major engineering education reforms: one is to develop CDIO curriculum syllabus with three Swedish universities in 2001, to emphasize the return of engineering education to engineering practice; The other is to release the survey report of MIT education task force for the future in 2014, ^[1] to advocate to the "project-based"; The third is to launch and implement the "new engineering education transformation" (NEET) plan in 2017, to comprehensively construct the new engineering education talent cultivation mode of "project-centered curriculum", which promoted the transformation of talent cultivation from discipline center to project center, that is, students aimed at completing the project under the support of related courses. ^[2] This is an important revelation for the reform of engineering education, especially for the mode of "project-centered curriculum" based on multi-disciplinary integration, which can be used for reference in the exploration of new engineering talent training in China.

The sustainability of the development of Open Education Resources (OER) is a global problem. Since UNESCO proposed OER in 2002, governments have attached great importance to the construction of OER projects. The European Commission launched the Open Education Action Plan; ^[3] The U.S. Department of Education has established a grant scheme to guarantee the construction, diffusion and evaluation of OER and redesign degree courses based on the OER Degree Program; ^[4] The Ministry of Education of China has set up a National High-quality Curriculum Project to provide financial guarantee for its development and maintenance, and also set up a teaching excellence award. ^[5] The CARE model proposed by the National Research Council of Canada and the OECD center for innovation in education research in 2018, which aimed to help individuals, institutions or organizations become excellent managers by developing and creating OER, reasonably classifying OER attributes or labels, sharing, publishing and spreading, and encouraging others to participate. ^[6] All of these help us deeply understand the importance of the construction of OER for continuing engineering education, and provide more new ideas for the implementation of long-term, systematic and practical lifelong education mode in the learner-centered learning society.

2 CONSTRUCTION OF NEW FRONTIER INTERDISCIPLINARY CONTINUING ENGINEERING EDUCATION AND TRAINING MODEL

With the rapid development of global economy and society, the formation and consolidation of core competitive advantages among countries, especially the competition for leading and dominant position in the development of global economy, science and technology and industry, all countries have cultivated outstanding engineering talents as their national strategy in the future.

In terms of training engineering science and technology talents for the future, the Chinese Academy of Sciences has done four main tasks in continuing engineering education:

- 1) Design project-oriented engineering education system on frontier cross field;
- 2) Establish a multi-terminal online and offline environment integrating OER for lifelong learning;
- 3) Research on point, line and surface-based mixed teaching model for engineering science and technology personnel;
- 4) Cooperate with other institutions to actively participate in the implementation process of the training program.

2.1 Project-led education training in cutting-edge cross

As the largest scientific research institution in China, the Chinese Academy of Sciences (hereinafter referred to as the CAS) aims to build an international first-class scientific research institution with important influence, attraction and competitiveness by 2020. The CAS will build a number of scientific research centres and innovation plateaus with distinctive academic characteristics and world influence in some areas of dominant disciplines, and actively participate in global innovation governance. This will play a positive role in promoting the training of high-level engineering talents in China.

In March 2017, the CAS officially issued the Outline of the 13th Five-Year Development Plan of the CAS (hereinafter referred to as the Outline of the Plan). In the Outline of Planning, it is pointed out that in the next five years, the CAS will put forward 60 breakthroughs and 80 key cultivation directions (excluding national defense scientific and technological innovation) which are expected to achieve leapfrogging development, involving organ repair and reconstruction, and tracing the causes of atmospheric haze, focusing on eight areas: Based on Cutting-edge Cross, Advanced Materials, Energy, Life and Health, Sea, Resources and Ecological Environment, Information Technology, Photoelectric Technology and the Space. The CAS, relying on its unique advantages, undertakes major scientific and technological projects oriented to economic and social factors, sustainable development and national security. Based on these cutting-edge projects, this paper constructs a project-guided mixed teaching (see Figure 1) to help engineering talents improve the integration ability of multi-disciplinary knowledge and enable them to understand the

scientific correlation and solve engineering problems in the face of complex engineering projects.

Fig. 1 Project-led mixed education training process in cutting-edge cross

The Project-based instructional design emphasizes that clear learning objectives should be taken as the start teaching, and instructional guidance plans should be formulated according to the learning evidence required by the standards and teaching activities to assist learners in learning. In order to enable learners accustomed to a complete way of solving problems, the "project" set up includes knowledge of many courses, and ultimately implements a complete "project" teaching activities.

In the online classroom environment, the knowledge unit of "micro-learning" guided by projects (microlecture on line) is designed, and then on the basis of these micro-knowledge units, a scientific chapter structure is combined to form a series of curriculum knowledge system. Finally, these systematic curriculum linkages are integrated into a logical relationship between professional frontier knowledge and ability training system courses and subject groups to help engineering science and technology talents to study in depth, expand and extend their thinking. In the offline classroom environment, it pay more attention to the interaction between lecturers and students, discuss and practice as the main means to explore the problems and solutions in actual projects and practical work.

2.2 Frontier Interdisciplinary syllabus design based on talent type

According to the differences of training objectives, the training of new engineering talents should be guided by the development path of talents in accordance with their aptitude, so as to achieve the ultimate goal of effectively training talents in the future. We design different teaching for two different talents by taking "Brain Science and Brain-like Intelligent computing" as an example (see Table 1).

Table 1. Frontier Interdisciplinary syllabus design based on talent type

Talent type	Project objectives	Frontier project guide	Frontier series of brain science courses	Frontier series of artificial intelligence courses	Course project
Academic type	Put forward innovative research ideas, verify them through experiments and data, and put them into practice to achieve the level of writing academic papers and participating in academic research	Academician frontier project microlecture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Human brainnetome atlas series 1. The winner-take-all choices 2. Brief introduction of neuroanatomy 3. The development of human brainnetome atlas 4. Cross - scale brainnetome atlas technique 5. Cross - scale brainnetome atlas: from rodents to primates 6. Human brainnetome atlas and its application 7. Application and case study of brain network atlas software 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data intelligence and deep learning series 1. The development and opportunity of big data management system 2. Scientific big data analysis 3. Scientific big data processing technology 4. Visualization and analysis of spatiotemporal data in scientific computing 5. Research progress and status of deep learning 6. Machine learning 7. Pattern recognition research 8. Case analysis of scientific research informatization 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Write a research paper 2. Complete a practical project of deep learning algorithms by integrating brain cognitive concepts
Professional type	Be able to combine theory with practice in discipline, technology and application, and be skilled in using tools and software to complete practical tasks	Associate researcher and above level key topic microlecture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Human brainnetome atlas series 1. Human brainnetome atlas and its application 2. Brief introduction of neuroanatomy 3. The development of human brainnetome atlas 4. Cross - scale brainnetome atlas technique 5. Introduction of brain network atlas and its drawing related technologies and methods 6. Multimodal brain imaging data processing software platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data intelligence and deep learning series 1. Development trend of information technology 2. Big data management technology and system 3. Big data and data intelligence 4. Data analysis techniques and visualization 5. General computing development status 6. Machine learning 7. Tensorflow foundation 8. Tensorflow platform framework and application practice 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use software to draw zonal brain atlas 2. Building the prototype of the latest generation of AI computing and data platform

3 INTEGRATING OER ONLINE AND OFFLINE IN LIFELONG LEARNING

3.1 WEB, APP multi-terminal intelligent environment construction

Continuing engineering education bears the heavy responsibility of updating the knowledge and improving the ability of new engineering and technical talents. Based on the "Intelligent Lifelong Learning Platform for Serving Talents Highland Construction", the CAS constructed the education and training system in frontier cross-field, and provided the online and offline integrated lifelong learning service for engineering talents. We actively cooperate with the Chinese Association of Science and Technology, colleges and universities to provide the high-quality resources to serve the lifelong education environment and the construction of continuing engineering talents (see Figure 2).

Fig. 2 WEB and APP multi-terminal intelligent environment support

3.2 Accumulation of a large number of OER

Based on the "Eight Areas" of the CAS, we have produced thousands of open education resources, and teased out conforms to continuing engineering education professional development and lifelong learning of 12 major series, including "The latest information technology and mathematics science", "Space exploration and manned space", "New energy and renewable energy use", "Health and health management", "The mysteries of life", "Environmental ecology and sustainable development", "Materials and engineering", "Ocean exploration and technology development", "Scientific literacy and scientific research ability", "Transformation of scientific and technological achievements and innovative entrepreneurship", "Cultural heritage and history of science", "Popular science", etc. The following pictures courses sample (see Figure 3).

Fig. 3 Courses sample

4 DESIGN A THREE-LEVEL CURRICULUM SYSTEM OF POINT-LINE-PLANE

4.1 Knowledge cycle system

Usually, new theories induce innovative methods and tools, that is, to transform theories into practical experience that knows how to implement them, and then to pursue new goals and experiences. This is the general law of human knowledge growth. Peter Senge and Daniel h. KIM figuratively compare it to a tree. The root is the theoretical support, the trunk is the method and tool support, and the final leaves and fruits are the practical knowledge nurtured. This system design will be based on the knowledge cycle construction, but the traditional teaching process lacks such a cycle process.

4.2 Point-line-surface design of knowledge structure

The system design is guided by knowledge points, micro-problems, micro-points and micro-lecture from the point of "fragmentation". Then it gives professional theoretical guidance and practical learning. It helps students to self-exercise and expand learning resources, to master learning methods and output learning results from three aspects of theory, method and practice, and finally form a knowledge tree in a certain field. And even the personal knowledge forest system. Micro learning is claimed to have positive effects on mastery learning and be an important part of blended learning. [7] In the construction of deep learning knowledge system, all knowledge information will be divided into small learning units, and then organized integration. Learning in small steps is made possible with the aid of small and well planned chunks of units or activities. [8] What we need to achieve is point-based micro-teaching design, line-based knowledge chapters design and face-based curriculum design and discipline groups (see Figure 4).

Fig. 4 Knowledge structure of point, line and surface

In the course of "Brain Science and Brain-like Intelligent computing", we have compiled a curriculum outline integrating "fragmentation" and "systematization" (see Table 2) to help students pay attention to the core knowledge points of each microlecture. At the same time, using multimedia technology, micro-lectures are divided into as small as possible knowledge fragments, which is convenient for mobile learning.

Table 2 Syllabus of human brainnetome atlas series (chapter 5 example)

Chapter	Section	Knowledge points	Topic & Question
The fifth chapter Human brainnetome atlas and its application	5.1 What makes a brain area distinct	Input-output connections, Connectional fingerprint, Patterns of gene expression, Criteria for human brain parcellation	What is the neocortex?
	5.2 Connectivity-based parcellation towards to human brainnetome atlas	Brain atlases: in vitro & in vivo, A framework for multimodal information integration, Connectivity-based parcellation(CBP), etc.	Why do we map the human brain network based on connection patterns?
	5.3 Applications of human brainnetome atlas in cognitive science	Anatomy and functions of PHR, Connectivity-based parcellation of PHR, etc.	What evidence can brain atlas provide for the memory system?
	5.4 Applications of human brainnetome atlas in clinical medicine	Precision therapy of brain diseases, Clinical applications in schizophrenia	Why is the brain atlas important in treating brain injury or mental illness?
	5.5 Applications of human brainnetome atlas in biological evolution	The nucleus accumbens, Parcellation results of the macaque Acb, rsFC profiles, Accumbens Shell and Core	According to brain atlas analysis, what is the biggest difference between the evolution of monkey brain and human brain?
	5.6 Applications of human brainnetome atlas in brain-like intelligence	From circuits to behavior, Brain-Inspired Computing, Brain connection pattern projection and mathematical algorithms	Does the drosophila olfactory system recognize odors through hash functions?
	5.7 Summary and prospect	Fine-grained anatomical parcels, Detailed anatomical and functional connections, etc.	What more valuable research can we do next?

4.3 Distribution of discipline groups oriented to frontier cross-cutting fields

In the aspect design of the above knowledge structure, a multi-disciplinary interdisciplinary subject group system had established. On the one hand, cutting-edge knowledge should be integrated to transfer closely related professional foundation and core courses. On the other hand, characteristic research and practice courses should be established to realize deep learning from cutting-edge cognition to basic consolidation and then to practical innovation, aiming to promote cross-field, cross-institution and cross-disciplinary engineering innovation personnel training (see Table 3).

Table 3 Distribution of frontier interdisciplinary groups (Listing some practices)

Frontier interdisciplinary direction	Direction of talents training	Frontier discipline system courses
Brain science and brain-like intelligent computing	Research and application of related personnel engaged in brain science, brain diseases and brain-like intelligence technology in cognitive neuroscience, neural network analysis, computational simulation of cognitive mechanism, brain heuristic computation, brain-computer interaction, etc.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Brain sciences 2. Cognitive analysis of brainnetome atlas 3. Cognitive mechanism calculation 4. Artificial intelligence integration
Precision medicine and health	Research and practical application of relevant personnel engaged in life science, clinical medicine, medicine and psychology in human genome, 4P medicine, precision medicine, precision drug therapy, precision health management, instrument use and other aspects	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The human genome 2. Precision medicine 3. Cancer screening and prevention 4. Drug research 5. Health management 6. Use of life science instruments

5 BREAKTHROUGH OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGY IN COURSES

The microlecture teaching platform represented by Khan Academy and MOOCs rises in foreign countries, but at the same time it also develops rapidly in China. The continuing engineering education of CAS created live broadcasting, three-point screen courses, green/blue virtual scene courses, electronic documents and other multimedia courseware by using advanced multimedia technology, so as to better integrate multimedia with education and achieve a breakthrough in educational informationization. The goal is to develop all kinds of teaching and aesthetic characteristics courses, help students understand the complex scientific content.

The virtual and real scenes are combined to enhance the immersive experience (see Figure 5). In the course of animation production, the two-dimensional animation element production is mainly completed by drawing, and the three-dimensional animation elements is mainly embodied in the modeling, mainly used in the cosmos, computational science, life science. We strive to keep pace with the international level by learning from TED-Ed. At the same time, in order to enhance the effect of online and offline learning, we use multimedia technology to build a live learning platform to

facilitate the large-scale coverage and dissemination of offline activities in continuing education (see Figure 6).

Fig. 5 Virtual scene synthesis

Fig. 6 Live of the congress of CAS

6 STRENGTHENING RESOURCES SHARING AND ACADEMIC EXCHANGE IN CONTINUING ENGINEERING EDUCATION

6.1 Collaborative education between universities and research institutes

Continuing engineering education undertakes the important task of renewing knowledge and improving ability of new engineering technical talents. The CAS has actively cooperated with the colleges and universities to provide the high-quality education services to more institutes in order to serve the lifelong education environment based on the learning society. For example, in cooperation with Beijing Open University, we had undertaken Beijing citizens' Lifelong Learning Curriculum Construction Projects in 2016 and 2017, and implemented the themes of "humanities and science", "career development", "improvement of teachers' scientific research ability", etc. It promoted the sharing of continuing engineering education resources. For example, in the humanities and sciences, integrating cutting-edge scientific and technological knowledge groups, such as information revolution, space journey, precision medicine in the digital age, environmental hot spots and sustainable development, we provide free lifelong education services for more than 20 million people in Beijing.

6.2 Actively participate world conference on continuing engineering education

The 16th International Association for Continuing Engineering Education (IACEE) has held at the University of Science and Technology Monterrey, Mexico, from May 22 to 25, 2018. The theme of the conference is "Shaping the Future of Continuing Education". More than 100 experts from various regions participated in the meeting to exchange research and future development trends of continuing engineering education. Yixia Zhao, the senior engineer in charge of the Continuing Education Network of the CAS, led the team members to participate in the meeting for international exchanges, and shared with Professor Patricio Montesinos of UPV University in Spain and Professor Clara Pioto of MIT the training experience of scientific research personnel management ability and e-Learning.

7 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

In order to support the informatization of the continuing education and training system, the CAS launched its Continuing Education Network in April 2016, providing lifelong learning services to nearly 70,000 employees. In 2018, 11588 researchers participated in 62359 training records. These training records come from 2137 training projects, including management skills training, on-the-job training, series of lectures, academic and thematic lectures, academic conferences, short-term special technology training, advanced professional and technical seminars and other training. Based on these research experts and special trainings, the CAS Continuing Education Network invites scientists to develop the large number of resources of Continuing Engineering Education, and to lay out the subject groups in cutting-edge. At present, it has accumulated thousands of courses. The CAS will effectively play the role of academicians, researchers and other scientists and engineers, to form a new mode of innovative talent training and contribute to the sustainable development of continuing engineering education.

REFERENCES

- [1] MIT. Institute-wide Task Force on the Future of MIT Education [EB/OL]. [2014-07-28]. http://web.mit.edu/future-report/TaskForceFinal_July28.pdf.
- [2] Exploring the impact of Margaret MacVicar's legacy on education at MIT [EB/OL]. [2017-04-06]. <http://odl.mit.edu/news-and-events/news/exploring-impact-margaret-macvicars-legacy-education-mit>.
- [3] Santos, A.I., Punie, Y., & Muñoz, J.C. (2016). Opening up education [EB/OL]. [2018-08-19]. <http://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC101436/jrc101436.pdf>.
- [4] Griffiths, R., Mislevy, J., Wang, S., et al. (2017). OER degree pathways [EB/OL]. [2018-08-19]. http://achievingthedream.org/system/files_force/resources/launching_oer_degree_pathways.pdf?download=1.
- [5] Wang, C. Y. & Zhao, G. D. (2011). Open educational resources in the People's Republic of China [EB/OL]. [2018-08-19]. <https://iite.unesco.org/pics/publications/en/files/3214700.pdf>.
- [6] Petrides, L., Levin, D., & Watson, C. E. (2018). Toward a sustainable OER ecosystem: The Case for OER Stewardship [EB/OL]. [2018-08-19]. <https://careframework.org/>.

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- [7] G. Sun, T. Cui, J. Yong, J. Shen, S. Chen, “Drawing micro learning into MOOC: Using fragmented pieces of time to enable effective entire course learning experiences”, IEEE International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work in Design, , 2015 :308-313.
- [8] D. Kovachev, Y. Cao, R. Klamma and M. Jarke, “Learn-as-you-go, New Ways of Cloud Based Micro-learning for the Mobile Web”, 10th International Conference on Web-based Learning, Hongkong, December 2011.